

CIPIS, Marcelo. **A lenda de Abelardo** [The legend of Abelard]. Illustrations Rogério Coelho. São Paulo: SM, 2017. (Barco a Vapor: série laranja).

REVIEW¹

Maria das Graças Monteiro Castro²

Author Dionisio Jacob has scripted several children's TV shows and received prizes such as the Jabuti for the best author of didactic and paradidactic in 2012 and the Fnlij Highly Recommended Seal in 2015. In *A lenda de Abelardo* (The Legend of Abelard), he narrates the life of a ten-year-old child who lives in a fief in the Middle Ages. It is a narrative full of adventure and fantasy, rich in the ambience of that time, which details the context and customs of the Middle Ages. The illustrations are vignettes that bring constitutive elements of the covered period..

Keywords: Middle Ages. Medieval History. Culture.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2018 Bologna. Books published in 2017 and reviewed in 2018. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

² Voter.